

A simple, rapid and highly sensitive magnetic beads ELISA for detection of SARS CoV-2 antibodies (IgG) in human plasma samples as point of the care assay

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Abstract:

Aim: Pandemic outbreak of coronavirus (SARS CoV-2) is going on for last 3 years. The people are vaccinated with different vaccines targeting S protein. Therefore, it is essential to have an assay, which can detect the different parts of virus as serological assay and can be performed as point of the care test, hence in this work, we decided to develop such assay with the help of magnetic beads.

Methods: The magnetic beads ELISA was developed in a microtube. The viral ligand specific magnetic beads were used to detect the nucleoprotein (NP) specific IgG antibodies in human plasma samples. The results were read with naked eyes as well as with professional ELISA readers.

Results: 7 μ l magnetic beads were suitable to detect the presence of NP specific antibodies. The assay needs only magnetic rack and pipettor to be performed. The results were available within 30 minutes. The positive results were observed as yellow color visually, but also read in ELISA reader as OD values. The sensitivity of this assay was $1:10^8$ dilutions. The cross-reaction panel was negative with different pathogens and negative human plasma.

Conclusion: In this work, it should be the first report in literature about the development of a magnetic beads ELISA as point of the care assay, which is reproducible, highly sensitive, robust and easy to perform. It was used to detect the presence of NP specific IgG antibodies in the plasma samples successfully. This assay can be used as professional assay, where the results can be measured with ELISA reader. This assay may be suitable in small clinics also under field conditions. It can be used to detect the SARS CoV-2 infection in vaccinated persons (S protein-based vaccines) along with non-vaccinated population in latent and active phase.

Keywords: Coronavirus, point of the care assay, serology, SARS CoV-2. Magnetic beads

Introduction: Magnetic beads are being used in biomedical and clinical research for different purposes like isolation of stem cells and mononuclear cells like T and B cells for last many years. (1, 2) Recent pandemic outbreak of SARS CoV-2 (Wuhan strain and its mutations) is going on for last 3 years as it started at the beginning of 2020. To detect this virus and its antibodies, there are different methods being used e.g. real time PCR tests and rapid tests are being used. (3) To detect the presence of SARS CoV-2 specific antibodies in blood and its fractions like plasma and serum, there is use of serological tests like ELISA, which are based on plates and these conventional ELISA needs many hours to provide the results. Therefore, scientific community is looking for alternatives to perform the ELISA in shorter time. (4-8)

Magnetic beads are being discussed in the literature as these may be an alternative because the magnetic beads tests can be finished quickly to give the results, moreover such tests can give results, which can be read with naked eye as well as in machine called ELISA reader. Such tests can act as point of the care also. (8) In literature, there are a few reports about magnetic beads ELISA tests. (9-12)

Most of vaccinations against SARS CoV-2 are based on S-protein in Europe and USA, hence the vaccinated persons should have antibodies against S-protein only. In case of natural infection, such persons are going to have antibodies against other parts of virus like Nucleoprotein (NP). Therefore, we decided to develop a magnetic beads ELISA assay to detect the NP specific antibodies in human plasma samples.

Methods: 100 µl Blocking puffer (Genekam, Germany) was pipetted in 1.5 ml microtubes (Starstedt, Germany) and to this, 7 µl or 10 µl of SARS CoV-2 ligand specific magnetic beads (Genekam) were added. These were kept at 5 minutes at room temperature. After that the fluid was removed, while keeping the tubes for 2 minutes in 6 tube magnetic rack (Genekam). The plasma or serum samples were diluted with diluting buffer 1:2 or 1:4 or more depending on the application. 100 µl of the diluted serum or plasma samples were added to magnetic beads and kept for 3 minutes at room temperature. The samples were washed with 1.5 ml washing buffer (Genekam) for 3 times. (Picture 1) 100 µl of conjugate anti human IgG was added to each well and kept at room temperature for 5 minutes. The magnetic beads were washed 4 times with 1.5 washing buffer. 100 µl of substrate was used in each well and kept for 7 minutes at room temperature in dark. The reactions were stopped with sulfuric acid solution. This will turn the color in yellow in positive samples but in negative control and samples, there is no color i.e., solution remains transparent. The results can be read with naked eye (Picture 2). To quantify the results, 100 µl of solution from each tube was put in 96 well plate. This plate was read in ELISA reader (BioBase, China) at 450nm wavelength. The whole test was finished within 30-45 minutes depending the number of samples tested. The whole procedure is the modification of conventional ELISA on the plates of the author research work.

This test was conducted with positive samples, positive as well as negative controls. In negative control, there were ligand specific magnetic beads, but only diluting buffer was added only. All experiments are conducted under sterile laminar flow. The positive controls were from NHS, UK.

The sensitivity was calculated with 10-fold serial dilution of 1:2 diluted positive samples. Cross-reaction panel included known positive samples for influenza, measles, Epstein Barr virus etc.

Results: The magnetic beads ELISA detects specifically positive samples for NP specific antibodies in plasma samples. The negative control was negative. There were around 4 unknown samples, which were positive for the presence of NP specific antibodies. These samples were repeated 3 times and they were also positive. The OD values measured with ELISA reader varies between 1.155 and 2.856. (Table 3) These results of these samples can be seen with the naked eyes as done with 10 experiments. (Picture 2) It means that this assay can be used as point of care under the field conditions. Cross reactions panel with related pathogens were negative. (Table 2). The reference samples from NHS, UK were positive too. ELISA reading was between 0.580 to 1.900 for different positive samples. Two different volumes of plasma 25 and 50 µl were used successfully.

The sensitivity limit of this assay is 10^8 . (Table 1)

It was found that 7 µl of ligand specific magnetic beads were sufficient to conduct the assay as at the beginning 10 µl of these were used, but it was found that 7 µl is optimal concentration to conduct the assay. The negative controls were negative with 7 µl magnetic beads against 10 µl magnetic beads. Where there is some problem of cross talking.

The time needed to perform, these magnetic beads assay was 30 minutes. It was found that this can be cut to 15 minutes, but the washing steps need a lot of time, which increases the time of conducting the assay. Genekam magnetic racks are made in such way that microtube fits in the rack tightly so that fluid can be thrown away just tilting the rack. The rest of fluid can be removed with pipette.

Discussion: In this research work, we have developed a magnetic beads ELISA for detecting the presence of NP specific antibodies (IgG) of SARS CoV-2. This can be used as point of care assay under the field conditions as this assay can be performed at the room temperature and it needs only magnetic rack as well as pipettor and its tips. This assay is highly sensitive as it can detect up to 10^8 dilutions, which should be more than detection limit of conventional ELISA. The reason may be that magnetic beads presents the antigen in 3D dimension against the conventional ELISA, where the antigens bind to the receptors at the plastic surface in 2D dimension. Another advantage is that the magnetic beads ELISA finished within 30 minutes against the conventional ELISA, which takes 3 to 24 hours. Our ELISA needs only 7 μ l antigen and it is very little. This can give the results with as little as 25 μ l plasma from patient.

We have developed using this basic method a number of magnetic ELISA tests against other pathogens as they are being validated and the work will be published later. Therefore, the small number of samples is shown in this paper. Not only this, this test has some other important applications also, which will be published later. Time needed to develop the whole assay was more than 5 years of research in our laboratory. We design new type of magnetic rack, where the tubes fit tightly in order to throw the supernatant while tilting the rack against the magnetic racks available on the market, where tubes shake and consume a lot of pipette tips to remove the supernatant and many times suck away the magnetic beads leading to failure.

Lucano et al. has developed magnetic beads ELISA for detection for SARS CoV-2 specific antibodies in 96 well plate system, but this test cannot be used under field conditions as it needs expensive instruments e.g., special magnetic rack and ELISA reader. This test can be used only in 96 wells plate system, hence it cannot be used as point of care assay because this assay is for professional laboratories, where user has full set up of instruments for serological assays, but our magnetic bead ELISA can be used worldwide as point of the care, where the results can be read through naked eyes as well as with ELISA reader, if user has it. The chemicals are in position to be transported easily. (13)

This assay is available as commercial test so that this can be used under field conditions for small clinics and mobile laboratories with limited sources in Europe as well as worldwide. The chemicals can be shipped at 4 °C or room temperature. This assay can be performed at room temperature. The cost of this assay is going to be around Euro 1 per test.

As this assay detects NP specific antibodies, hence this can be used to detect the presence of these antibodies in vaccinated and infected persons with active and latent infection.

Conclusion: It may be first report in literature about magnetic ELISA test for detection SARS CoV-2 antibodies in plasma samples with a highly sensitive assay as point of care along having the possibility to quantify the concentration of antibodies with a ELISA reader. Point of the care assay needs only simple instruments like magnetic rack, pipettors and pipette tips. It can be conducted anywhere worldwide.

Funding: This is self-funded, hence there is no external funding.

Acknowledgement: Ms Kornelia Niklis has assisted during the performing the assays and Mr Stephan Suppers did the graphic art.

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Table 1 showing sensitivity range with different dilutions.

Dilutions	Result
1 : 0	positive
1 : 10	positive
1 : 100	positive
1 : 1000	positive
1 : 10000	positive
1 : 100000	positive
1 : 1000000	positive
1: 10000000	positive
1 : 100000000	positive
1: 1000000000	negative
1: 10000000000	negative

Table 2 showing cross reactions panel.

Pathogen	Result
Influenza A	negative
Mumps	negative
EBV	negative
Human Plasma	negative
Measles	negative

Table 3 is showing the OD values of different plasma samples with magnetic beads.

Plasma (OD values)					
Experiment	1	2	3	4	5
Plasma sample	2.116	2.852	2.840	1.155	2.386
Negative control	0.082	0.091	0.078	0.069	0.09

Picture 1 Magnetic rack with microtubes inside is showing washing step.

Picture 2 The yellow color is indicating the positive samples and transparent color is indicating negative control.